

EFFECT OF LOW-DOSE INTRAVENOUS DEXMEDETOMIDINE ON RECOVERY FROM GENERAL ANESTHESIA IN LAPAROSCOPIC CHOLECYSTECTOMY

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Abstract

Objective: To compare the effect of low-dose dexmedetomidine versus normal saline on the basis of the frequency of cough and poor Steward recovery score.

Methods: In this randomized controlled trial, we included 60 patients who were planned for laparoscopic cholecystectomy under general anesthesia. The patients were recruited from February 2023 to August 2023 from the general surgery unit of Services Hospital Lahore. Group D received an intravenous administration of 0.3 µg/kg dexmedetomidine, diluted in a 20 ml syringe and infused over 10 minutes following the induction of anesthesia. Meanwhile, Group NS was administered 20 ml of normal saline over the same time frame. Incidence of cough and poor steward recovery score was noted after extubation.

Results: In the study, the participants had an average age of 34.8 (±7.67) years. The gender distribution included 28 (46.7%) males and 32 (53.3%) females. In terms of cough incidence, Group D reported 6 cases (20.0%), while Group N had a considerably higher incidence, with 19 cases (63.3%) (P-value <0.0001). Additionally, when assessing the Poor Steward Recovery Score, Group D had 11 participants (36.7%) with a poor score compared to 21 participants (70%) in Group N (P-value 0.019).

Conclusion: Low-dose dexmedetomidine (0.3 µg/Kg) after induction of anesthesia is effective in reducing the incidence of cough and improving the steward recovery score after extubation.

INTRODUCTION

During general anesthesia, airway management is primarily achieved through laryngoscopy and intubation. These procedures stimulate both mechanical and chemical responses within the body. Such stimuli often provoke adverse reactions, including coughing, agitation, increased blood pressure, and tachycardia, with coughing alone occurring in as many as 82.5% of cases.¹ Coughing during the removal of the ETT can cause not only discomfort for the patient but also lead to serious complications including increased blood pressure,

rapid heartbeat, heart ischemia, and laryngospasm.² During laparoscopic procedures, the creation of a pneumoperitoneum and elevated carbon dioxide levels (hypercapnia) can stimulate the sympathetic nervous system, resulting in elevated blood pressure and heart rate. Additionally, hypercapnia has been linked to enhanced cough reflexes. Various methods have been explored to ensure a more comfortable and safe extubation process, such as the use of intravenous lidocaine and remifentanyl.^{3,4}

Dexmedetomidine is a derivative of imidazole that exhibits a high affinity for alpha-2 adrenergic receptors. These receptors are distributed throughout various regions, including: (i) blood vessels, where they influence vasodilation; (ii) sympathetic nerve endings, where they inhibit norepinephrine release; (iii) the central nervous system, affecting sedation levels and vagal activity; and (iv) the spinal cord, contributing to pain relief.⁵ Multiple studies have indicated that dexmedetomidine can effectively mitigate the body's stress response to surgery and maintain BP during procedures. Additionally, it has been demonstrated to decrease the requirements for anesthetic agents and enhance postoperative recovery quality.^{6, 7} Consequently, dexmedetomidine has become a common adjunct in general anesthesia protocols. The aim of the present study was to compare the effect of low-dose dexmedetomidine versus normal saline on the basis of the frequency of cough and poor Steward recovery score.

Methods:

In this randomized controlled trial, we included 60 patients who were planned for laparoscopic cholecystectomy under general anesthesia. The patients were recruited from February 2023 to August 2023 from the general surgery unit of Services Hospital Lahore. Patients with diabetes, cardiopulmonary disease, metabolic disorders, renal disease (Creatinine >1.3 mg/dL), allergic to study drugs, history of PONV, and history of motion sickness were excluded.

A total of sixty patients were randomized into two groups of thirty using a lottery system. Group D received an intravenous administration of 0.3 µg/kg dexmedetomidine, diluted in a 20 ml syringe and infused over 10 minutes following the induction of anesthesia. Meanwhile, Group NS was administered 20 ml of normal saline over the same time frame. Upon arrival in the operating room, all patients had a 20G cannula inserted, and monitoring equipment including ECG, pulse oximetry, and non-invasive blood pressure cuffs were set up. To alleviate anxiety, each patient was given midazolam at a dose of 0.02 mg/kg. After three minutes of preoxygenation, anesthesia was initiated with propofol (2 mg/kg) and nalbuphine (0.08 mg/kg), while tracheal intubation was facilitated with atracurium at a dose of 0.5

mg/kg. Maintenance of anesthesia was achieved using isoflurane at 1.5% and 60% nitrous oxide in oxygen, with patients ventilated in a volume-controlled manner. Following abdominal insufflation with carbon dioxide, lung mechanics were adjusted to ensure normocapnia, targeting an end-tidal carbon dioxide level of 35-40 mm Hg, and intra-abdominal pressure was kept between 12 and 15 mm Hg. Thirty minutes before concluding the surgery, all patients received an infusion of paracetamol at 1 mg/kg and 4 mg of ondansetron as a preventive measure against postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV). Neuromuscular reversal was accomplished with neostigmine at 0.05 mg/kg along with atropine administered at 0.02 mg/kg. Cough severity was evaluated in the recovery room at five minutes post-extubation using a four-point scale: 0 representing no cough, 1 indicating minimal (single) cough, 2 for moderate cough lasting less than 5 seconds, and 3 for severe cough lasting longer than 5 seconds. A cough was deemed significant if the score exceeded 2. The Steward Recovery Score was assessed 5 minutes after extubation, with a score below 4 classified as a poor recovery score.

The data were entered into SPSS software version 24.0. The comparison of cough and poor steward scores between groups was conducted using the Chi-square test, with a significance level set at $p \leq 0.05$.

RESULTS:

In the study, the participants had an average age of 34.8 (± 7.67) years. The gender distribution included 28 males, accounting for 46.7% of the group, and 32 females, representing 53.3%. The mean weight of the individuals was 60.5 (± 10.25) kilograms. The duration of the surgeries averaged 52.8 (± 8.49) minutes (Table 1).

In a comparison of study outcomes between two groups. In terms of cough incidence, Group D reported 6 cases (20.0%), while Group N had a considerably higher incidence, with 19 cases (63.3%) (P-value <0.0001. Additionally, when assessing the Poor Steward Recovery Score, Group D had 11 participants (36.7%) with a poor score compared to 21 participants (70%) in Group N, which yielded a P-value of 0.019. These findings highlight notable disparities in both cough incidence and recovery outcomes between the two groups (Table 2).

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics.

Age (Years)	34.8±7.67
Gender (male/Female)	28 (46.7%) / 32 (53.3%)
Weight (Kg)	60.5±10.25
Duration of Surgery (mins)	52.8±8.49

Table 2. Comparison of Study Outcomes.

	Group D (N=30)	Group N (N=30)	P-value
Cough (%)	06 (20.0%)	19 (63.3%)	<0.0001
Poor Steward Recovery Score (%)	11 (36.7%)	21 (70%)	0.009

DISCUSSION:

During general anesthesia, procedures such as intubation, creating pneumoperitoneum, and extubation act as significant stressors to the body. These stimuli can provoke a robust stress response, leading to increased production of catecholamines like adrenaline and noradrenaline in the bloodstream. As a result, patients often experience rises in heart rate and blood pressure, which can precipitate serious complications, especially in individuals with pre-existing cardiovascular or cerebrovascular conditions. These complications may include myocardial ischemia, various arrhythmias, and cerebrovascular events.^{8, 9} Dexmedetomidine targets specific receptors in the brain and spinal cord, namely the α 2A, α 2B, and α 2C subtypes, to produce a variety of therapeutic effects such as sedation, anxiety reduction, pain relief, and sympathetic nervous system suppression. When the α 2A receptors in the brainstem's vasomotor center are activated, they diminish norepinephrine release, which can cause blood pressure to drop and slow the heart rate. Additionally, stimulating the α 2A and α 2C receptors in the locus coeruleus induces sedation. In the spinal cord, activation of these receptors inhibits substance P release, a neuropeptide involved in pain signaling, thereby directly reducing pain perception and providing analgesic effects.¹⁰ Coughing during the recovery phase after general anesthesia, particularly following extubation, is a frequent issue that can result in complications such as hemodynamic instability, laryngospasm, wound disruption, and bleeding.¹¹ To mitigate the occurrence of cough during this period,

dexmedetomidine (Dex) is often utilized due to its effective sedative, analgesic, and sympatholytic properties.¹² Our findings indicated that administering Dex at a dose of 0.3 μ g/kg significantly lowered both the frequency and intensity of coughing. Research has shown a correlation between the dosage of Dex and the likelihood of coughing during emergence from anesthesia.¹³ While a higher Dex dosage may enhance sedation, it is often associated with prolonged recovery times post-surgery.¹⁴

Our findings in this study demonstrate that premedication with intravenous Dex 0.3 μ g/kg before anesthesia induction is effective in attenuating intraoperative stress response, in reducing the incidence of cough and in improving the steward recovery score.

Ye Q et al. investigated the effects of dexmedetomidine on intraoperative hemodynamics, recovery, and postoperative pain in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy. They found that administering 0.6 μ g/kg of dexmedetomidine intravenously before induction helps maintain stable hemodynamics, reduces cough during emergence, and alleviates postoperative pain. Compared to the normal saline group, the incidence of cough during emergence was significantly lower in the D2 (0.6 μ g/kg) and D3 (0.8 μ g/kg) groups (70% in the saline group versus 26.67% and 23.33% in D2 and D3 groups).¹¹

In a study by Munise et al., the recovery scores were reported to be >4 in 56% of the dexmedetomidine group and 4% of the normal saline group after 5 minutes of extubation (P <0.05).¹⁵

A similar study by Xu et al. also observed a smooth and favorable recovery in patients undergoing Endoscopic Sinus Surgery under general anesthesia, with intraoperative infusion of dexmedetomidine.¹⁶ This research has several limitations. Firstly, the number of participants was limited, which may have affected the statistical reliability and introduced some deviations. Secondly, the study did not explore how varying doses of Dex premedication might influence outcomes. Prior research indicated that different doses of Dex have varying anesthetic effects, and based on our previous findings, we determined that a dose of 0.3 µg/kg of Dex is optimal for premedication in this context.

CONCLUSION:

Low-dose dexmedetomidine (0.3 µg/Kg) after induction of anesthesia is effective in reducing the incidence of cough and improving the steward recovery score after extubation.

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